

**PROBLEMATIC DISCUSSIONS ABOUT THE AUTHOR OF THE WORKS
“GUL VA BULBUL” (“FLOWER AND NIGHTINGALE”)**

Surayya Shodiyeva Salahiddin kizi

Qashqadaryo viloyati Qarshi shaharimi

Doctoral student of Karshi State University, Karshi, Uzbekistan

surayyoshodiyeva92@gmail.com

Annotation: This article describes the authors of the work "Flower and Nightingale", in particular, the authors of the work "Flower and Nightingale" by Salahi, who lived in Kashgar in the XVIII century, and the author of the work of the same name by Salahi, who created in Karshi in the XVIII century. Theoretical and practical evidence of these problematic ideas are provided.

Key words: Salahi, kashgharlik, "Flower and Nightingale", source, stone print, praise, na't, me'rojnomas, image, mystical work, divine love.

Introduction

In the history of our literature of the XVII-XIX centuries, a number of writers who wielded the pen under the pseudonym "Salahi" grew up. It is surprising that in these times there were also writers who wrote the same work under this pseudonym. In order to distinguish writers with similar pseudonyms and their works from each other, we found it permissible to dwell briefly on them. One of them is a writer with the pseudonym Salahi, who lived in Kashgar in the XVII century. His epic “Gul va Bulbul” (Flower and Nightingale) is stored in the main fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies named after Beruniy of the UzRFA in inventory numbers 3402-II and 5354. Among these sources, 3402-II is considered to be a complete copied copy of the epic, while the manuscript book numbered inv. 5354 contains a fragment of the epic from pages 21 to 45. 3402-I contains 8 pages of wise words. Inv.3402-II is Salahi's work “Gul va Bulbul” (Flower and Nightingale), it consists of pages 10 to 89, a total of 79 pages. The book is red, with a thick cover, yellow edges, on Kokan paper. This source is well preserved, but some parts were torn. It was written in the Turkish language in the nastaliq letter, the copyist and the year are not known.

Purpose and mission

Salahi's XVIIth-century epic “Gul va Bulbul” (Flower and Nightingale) and Salahiddin Salahi's work, created in the XVIIIth century, are extremely similar, that is, the composition, subject, images, and ideas of both epics are common. Even some literary scholars made a lot of mistakes in their scientific research due to not distinguishing the works of both Salahi. For example, Professor Khalid Rasul and Ph.D., Shakhnoza Rakhmonova studied the saga of Salahi from Kashgar as the work

of Salahiddin Salahi. Therefore, in order to avoid such confusion, below we will compare some of the differences between the works of Khagharism and the resistance of Salahi.

Research methods

In writing this scientific article, observation, comparison, description and historical-comparative, biographical, statistical, contextual and complex research methods were used based on the principles of historicity, objectivity, scientificity.

Results and comments

First, in the preface to his work, Salahi from Kashgar mentioned that he wrote his epic under the influence of Gurbati's book "Gul-u Bulbul":

Saying that Gurbatikim is a book,
Let go of the Gul-u Bulbul book.
Bayan etmis Gul-u Bulbul's ishqin...
How many verses and gazals,
As he said, the villages.
The book is good, but
It's been a long time, but it's cracked...
This book is a kindness,
What I did was to sympathize with Gurbati...
I cleaned the book of Gurbati,
I made a sheet of Shiroza in Fasur.
That I did the severance,
Salahi's hair is a gem.

The author emphasized that his epic is similar to the works of the XVIIth-century poet Sufi Olloyor, and that it brings joy and excitement to people of true love:

Add a word to the book Gurbati,
Blink your eyes to the word Olloyor.⁵

In the following stanza, the place where the work was written, that is, the name of the country and its history, is mentioned:

Bolub faizi bohar Koshgardin,
Take the dardi ishqiyotdin of ta'rix.
Boluban migrated to Mustafa,
These are the words I found and enjoyed.⁶

From the combination of "dardi ishqiyat" in the second verse of this verse, the year of writing of the work is 1089 Hijri. It corresponds to 1678 AD. So, it is clear from these verses that Salahi wrote his work in 1678 in Kashgar. The above-

⁵ Salohiy. Gul va Bulbul. O'zRFA Sharqshunoslik institutining qo'lyozmalar fondi. Inv.3402-II. – B 14-15.

⁶ That work. – B 15 (b).

mentioned history was also recorded by a researcher of the Institute of Oriental Studies on the first page of the book (as additional information).

Secondly, the saga of Salahiddin Salahi begins with a description of the main events. The work of Salahi from Kashgar began with traditional praise, praise and prayer:

"Lav lak" was also in honor of Muhammad
This is because of Mustafa,
Know the miracle of "shaqq ul-qamar",
My life is dedicated to him.
He pointed out that it was two months ago,
Fu chuq (shu chak) ul moon futun appeared.
Seeing the miracle of Muhammad,
Most of the efforts brought faith.
Muhammad jilvagoh arsh farshi,
Hashim will build the generation of Ki.
Beloved of God erdi ul Muhammad,
Muhammad was remembered by God Ahmed.
Muhammaddur habibi Haq Taalo,
May Allah bless you Mawla.
Muhammad is alive like a human being.
He is a prophet to the crown of Hama.
God's friend is a prophet,
His close friend is Muhammad Mustafadur⁷.

In the first verse, a hadith with the meaning "Lav lak", i.e. "Lav laka lama kholaqtu-l-aflok" - ("O Muhammad, if it were not for you, I would not have created these heavens") is quoted. A hadith with the same meaning was revealed when the Prophet, peace be upon him, ascended the Miraj. "Lav lak" in this verse is an example of the art of quotation, and this is exactly what Salahi is referring to. Salahi noted that the hadith "Lav Lak" is in honor of our Prophet and that Allah's purpose in creating the whole universe was taken as the reason for Muhammad's existence. Also, in the above verse, the incident of "shaqq ul-qamar" referring to Surah "Qamar" is also mentioned. The explanation of this is given in the Holy Qur'an as follows: "The polytheists of Makkah said to the Prophet (s.a.v.): "If you split the moon in the sky in two, we will believe in you." This miracle happened when Rasulullah (s.a.w.) prayed to God...⁸ The sentence ends with the fact that God's closest friend is the Prophet, that is, Muhammad Mustafa.

⁷ Salohiy. Gul va Bulbul. O'zFA SHI, qo'lyozma inv 3402-II. – B 10.

⁸ Qur'oni Karim (ma'nolar tarjimasi; Abdulaziz Mansurov). www.ziyouz.com kutubxonasi. – B 367.

In the following verses, the sentence that is the basis of the saying of the Prophet "My poverty is my pride" is presented. In addition, there are also comments about the fact that he is from the generation of sayyids, that he has the keys to the eight heavens, that he went to Miraj, and that he believed in Mustafa, a true friend of God:

Muhammad is the pride of the whole world,

Muhammad was the pride of al-fakr.

A man of the generation of Sayyid Muhammad,

Muhammed to all the prophets.

Mahram to walk like Muhammad,

The creator is great.

The hope of the whole nation,

He has the keys to eight airplanes in his hands.

He wished the ummah to go out,

The sinner ate the grief of the community.

I thank God, the ummah,

Anga brought faith to our language.

Dardi benihoya Mustafa,

God's friend, that is, Mustafa.

Thank you Nabiullah Ahmed,

Intercession, O Messenger of Allah, Muhammad.

Saying that he is the ummah of Muhammad, Salahi prays for him to intercede for him. After that, the statement of the Chaharors (four caliphs) is given:

Na't to you, my hope is from you

.....It's your turn to conquer me,

Intercede for your righteous people

Do not die in despair

Alqabu chaharyar rizwanullahi alayhim ajma'in

He said and applauded the cheerleaders,

They are so happy and happy

Bayon aylay Muhammad chahoryori,

Companionship has four advantages ...⁹

Thirdly, the main events of the saga of Salahi from Kashgar are presented after the chapter called "Sababi nazmi kitab" and it begins with the following verses:

Both, O heart, sympathize,

The Safo is a flower and a nightingale.

To Flower Nightingale, the lover, did not change.

The love story of Nightingale is the story of Flower.¹⁰

⁹ Salohiy. Gul va Bulbul. O'zFASHI, qo'lyozma inv 3402-II. – B 11.

¹⁰ That work, – B 44.

As for the main events of Salahiddin Salahi's saga, it started directly with the content similar to the verse above:

Both, O heart, sympathize,
The Safo is a flower and a nightingale.
To Flower Nightingale, who is in love, is no stranger.
The love story Nightingale kasd Flower.¹¹

Fourthly, the naming of the chapters and the similar and different aspects of the verses related to it are also noticeable:

In Salahi of Kashgar:
Led by Sabo to Nightingale (chapter name)
Sabo shakes his body accusingly of Raptor,
Bolub to Nightingale is just one leader.¹²

In Salahiddin Salahi:
Sabo to Nightingale is the leader (chapter name)
The puck shakes with Sabo raftorin,
Bolub is the leader of Nightingale¹³.

Kashgarlik Salahi:
Nightingale died in love with red Flower. The world that bought the nightingale killed itself (chapter name)

A narrator narrated to me,
Mundog told a wonderful story.
Because of the love of the flower, the nightingale smoked a sigh,
He died with a sigh.

Salahiddin Salahi:
The Nightingale Sighed and Died (chapter title)
The narrator narrated to me,
Mundog made a wonderful complaint.
That the nightingale smoked in the love of the flower,
He suddenly died with a sigh.¹⁴

Fifth, pseudonyms are given in both works, and they are used as follows:

Kashgarlik Salahi:
O Lord, forgive sins,
God, forgive, you are the Forgiver¹⁵.

In this stanza, the poet addresses the Creator as "God" using the art of exclamation and mentions his sinfulness. In the second verse, asking for forgiveness

¹¹ Salohiy. Gul va Bulbul. O'zFASHI, toshbosma inv 577. – B 2.

¹² Salohiy. Gul va Bulbul. O'zFASHI, qo'lyozma inv 3402-II. – B 83.

¹³ Salohiy. Gul va Bulbul. O'zFASHI, toshbosma inv 577. – B 43.

¹⁴ That work, – B 46.

¹⁵ Salohiy. Gul va Bulbul. O'zFASHI, qo'lyozma inv 3402-II. – B 89.

for his sins, he mentions the name Gafar, one of the 99 names of Allah, and laments, "you are Gafar."

Salahuddin Salahi:

Thank you, God bless you.

The book Gul-u Bulbul was completed.¹⁶

Sixthly, the end of the saga of Salahi from Kashghar is not similar to the work of Salahiddin Salahi.

If there is a mistake in the word, it is a defect,

Know, make my body beautiful.

(Tammāt al-Kitāb bi'awni Maliki Wahhab)

Shud batawfiq Khudoyi La Yanom

The book fast is over on Wednesday.

I don't have a letter, don't blame my letter!

Don't forget the prayer while reading this book.

Don't read my letter if you see it.

Curse me, don't curse me.¹⁷

Summary It is known from the above thoughts and the content of the given verse that the work of Salahi from Kashghar and the work of Salahiddin Salahi are considered to be separate works. From the point of view of the period in which he lived, we can say that Salahiddin Salahi wrote his work under the influence of the epic “Gul va Bulbul” (Flower and Nightingale) by Salahi from Kashghar, and as compensation for it.

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¹⁶ Salohiy. Gul va Bulbul. O'zFASHI, toshbosma inv 577. – B 48.

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